

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP7 – Information and data governance, ethics, technology and data catalogue and quality support

D7.22 Report confirming that all the relevant documents for using animal experiments (WP3) prior to the start of the research activity raising ethics issue and that they are kept on file

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Abstract

Started in 2019, the ConcePTION project aims to establish a large ecosystem to provide fast and reliable evidence on drug safety during pregnancy and breastfeeding. ConcePTION partners are conducting studies across Europe, some of them with the close collaboration of pregnant and breastfeeding women, which is one of the cornerstones of the project.

As described in the research proposal, certain tasks in work packages 3 involve the use of animals to perform some of the studies pre-specified in the DoA. In this report on deliverable D7.22, we describe the collection and availability of the ethical documentation for work package 3.

Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
DP	Demonstration Project
WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of Action
IRB	Institutional Review Board
DMP	Data Management Plan
UNIBO	Università di Bologna

Purpose and scope of this document

One of the purposes of WP7 in the ConcePTION project is to provide ethical, governance, and quality assessment support for the conduct of distributed data collection and analyses which facilitates the generation of high quality real world evidence. Task 7.10 involves collecting copies from all templates, Institutional Review Board (IRB) comments and approvals, and further related documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical and IMI obligations.

The purpose of deliverable D7.22 is to describe the collection of ethical documentation of the activities carried out within work package 3 (WP3) that involves the use of animals for certain experimental tasks within the ConcePTION project, with the aim to demonstrate how studies comply with current ethical and local governance requirements.

From the ConcePTION Description of Action (DoA), D7.22 description is:

“Report confirming that all relevant documents for using animal experiments (WP3) prior to the start of the research activity raising ethics issue and that they are kept on file

Background

ConcePTION aims to create an ecosystem for the rapid and robust generation of evidence on the safety of medications in pregnancy and lactation, using both existing and newly generated real-world data. The present report is one of the five deliverables in task 7.10 and involves our partners from WP3.

Task 7.10 of WP7 is described as follows in the ConcePTION Description of Action (DoA):

“In this task we will collect copies from all templates, IRB review comments and approvals and documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical (see section 5) and IMI obligations. This task will deliverable five deliverables (D7.18-7.22), providing proof and documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant.”

WP3 focusses on the determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation by generation quantitative and translatable data. In particular, task 3.3 within WP3 comprises the use of animal lactation models (*in vivo* experiments using Gottingen minipigs and/or pig farm breed).

Work Package 3

The main objective of WP3 is to develop, characterise, validate, and apply a non-clinical testing platform for reliable prediction of drug concentrations in human breast milk along with systemic drug exposure in breastfed infants. The particular aim of task 3.3 is to develop and characterise an *in vivo* model for drug passage from maternal blood to human breast milk. These *in vivo* studies will use innovative designs considering the possibility for micro-dosing, cassette dosing and blood sampling in offspring. Such approaches are expected to maximise the amount of data generated in the animal model, consistent with the 3R principle (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) on welfare of animals.

The preclinical *in vivo* studies in lactating minipigs will be performed at two sites: LabCorp UK and UNIBO. Briefly, task 3.3 in WP3 comprises 8 projects using animal lactation models listed below:

1. Production of primary mammary epithelial cells from Gottingen pigs as a replacement/reduction method (UNIBO)
2. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (UNIBO) - *Amoxicillin*
3. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (UNIBO) - *Venlafaxine*
4. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (UNIBO) – *Metformin*
5. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (UNIBO) – *Levocetirizine*
6. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp) - *Metformin*
7. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp) – *Venlafaxine*
8. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp) - *Cetirizine*
9. Evaluation of mammary excretion of pharmacologically active molecules following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp) - *Amoxicillin*

Task description

This deliverable report is based on the collection of ethical documentation, that is – templates, informed consent procedures, informed consent sheets, participant’s information sheets, Standard Operational Procedures (SOP), Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval, and Data Management Plan (DMP) and Data Impact Protection Assessment (DPIA), if applicable. The aim is to provide proof and public documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant their ethical and local governance requirements.

The scope of this particular delivery is ethical and governance documentation related to studies in which animals are use. It is not part of this deliverable to monitor or audit whether information provision, consent procedures, and ethical approvals were conducted according to national/regional guidelines or local requirements where the studies will take place or whether they followed the recommendation from the ConcePTION consortium ([Singleton & Cunnington 2020](#)).

From September 2022 to September 2023, we approached WP and DP leads via e-mail requesting the aforementioned documentation. [Table 1](#) shows the studies, the documentation shared, name of the files, and the contact person who handled the documentation till the moment of the submission of the present report. We expect partners to still contribute to this ‘live’ report with further documentation once they received approvals by uploading files in the corresponding WP folder in the IMI-ConcePTION Member area.

Table 1. Ethical documentation for WP3

STUDY	DOCUMENTATION SHARED WITH WP7	NAME OF THE FILE IN IMI-CONCEPTION MEMBER AREA	CONTACT PERSON IN WP3
Production of primary mammary epithelial cells from Gottingen pigs as a replacement/reduction method (UNIBO)	<input type="radio"/> Protocol <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	3b-AutRigMinistero[1181]Approvazione_notifica_BDN_Forni_1181.pdf	Monica Forni Monica.Forni[at]unibo[dot]it
Evaluation of mammary excretion of amoxicillin following systemic administration in lactating sows (UNIBO)	<input type="radio"/> Protocol <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	3c-AutRigMinistero[1185]Approvazione_202132 _Forni_1185.pdf new pdf	Maria Laura Bacci Marialaura.Bacci[at]unibo[dot]it
Evaluation of mammary excretion of metformin following systemic administration in lactating sows (UNIBO)*	<input type="radio"/> Protocol <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	AutRigMinisterio[1282]Autorizzazione_202335_Bacci_1282.pdf	Maria Laura Bacci Marialaura.Bacci[at]unibo[dot]it
Evaluation of mammary excretion of venlafaxine following systemic administration in lactating sows (UNIBO)*	<input type="radio"/> Protocol <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	AutRigMinisterio[1282]Autorizzazione_202335_Bacci_1282.pdf	Maria Laura Bacci Marialaura.Bacci[at]unibo[dot]it
Evaluation of mammary excretion of levocitrizine following systemic administration in lactating sows*	<input type="radio"/> DMP <input type="radio"/> Protocol <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval	AutRigMinisterio[1282]Autorizzazione_202335_Bacci_1282.pdf	Maria Laura Bacci Marialaura.Bacci@unibo.it
Evaluation of mammary excretion of metformin	<input type="radio"/> Protocol <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> IRB approval		Brian Anderson brian.anderson@labcorp.com

following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp)**

<p>Evaluation of mammary excretion of venlafaxine following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp)**</p>	<p><input type="radio"/> Protocol <input type="radio"/> IRB approval</p>	<p>Brian Anderson brian.anderson@labcorp.com</p>
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Evaluation of mammary excretion of cetirizine following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp)**

<p>Evaluation of mammary excretion of amoxicillin following systemic administration in lactating sows (LabCorp)**</p>	<p><input type="radio"/> Protocol <input type="radio"/> IRB approval</p>	<p>Brian Anderson brian.anderson@labcorp.com</p>
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✓ Available in IMI-ConcePTION Member Area.

○ Not available. Contact work package lead for further information.

* These studies share the same IRB approval.

** These studies are still in planning stages

Availability

We proposed to make the documentation available via the [IMI-ConcePTION Member Area](#) to allow related WP leads/members to upload their documentation after the date of submission of this deliverable, if deemed necessary. Each WP has been assigned a folder in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area where they can store related documentation in the following path: IMI-ConcePTION Member Area/Work package 3/2-Ethics Deliverables/in vivo studies (Figure 1).

The present report will be made available as 'Files' in the public repository ([Zenodo – IMI ConcePTION](#)), after approval of this report. The report will be public in the public domain and available for download.

Figure 1. Preview of repository for related documentation.

Documents

The screenshot shows a file repository interface. The breadcrumb path is "Work package 3 > 2- Ethics Deliverables > In vivo studies". A search bar is present with the placeholder "Enter search term". Below the breadcrumb, there are "Views" and "Actions" tabs. The "Views" tab is active, showing a list of files. The "Actions" tab contains icons for file operations. The file list has columns for "Name", "Date modified", and "Size".

	Name	Date modified	Size
<input type="checkbox"/>	3b- AutRigMinistero[1181]Approvazione_Notifica_BDN_Forni_1181.pdf	11/10/2022 3:35 PM	454.2 KB
<input type="checkbox"/>	3c- AutRigMinistero [1185]Autorizzazione_202132_Bacci_1185.pdf new.pdf	11/10/2022 3:57 PM	162.7 KB
<input type="checkbox"/>	AutRigMinistero[1282]Autorizzazione_202335_Bacci_1282.pdf	8/11/2023 5:05 PM	789.0 KB

At the bottom left, there is a "Items per Page:" dropdown set to "10". At the bottom right, it shows "3 Items".

Conclusion

The present Report provides an overview of the ethical documentation related to the use of animals in experiments within WP3. Until the submission of this deliverable, UNIBO and LabCorp have provided the documentation stated on this report through the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area. Nonetheless, two studies are still in planning stage (Venlafaxine and Cetirizine-LabCorp). We expect further ethical documentation to be made available through the same media after the approval of this deliverable.

References

Singleton, P., & Cunnington, M. (2020). Report on initial information and research governance for WP1-5 (D7.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5840292>